

Tobi, your i2i ambassador

SUMMARY

Evidence-Based Approaches to Addressing Sexual Violence: Innovations in HIV Prevention and Support

The magnitude of SV

Women and girls' experience of sexual violence (SV) is prevalent across geographies.

15-24 year-olds experience Intimate Partner Violence (IPV) in their lifetime

Women who experienced physical or sexual IPV were significantly more likely to acquire HIV. Persons who have recently acquired HIV experience higher rates of SV

EVIDENCE REVIEW

Much of the evidence to-date on addressing SV among adolescent girls and young women has emerged from high-income country contexts. Our review set out to better understand what types of SV intervention have been implemented in low- and middle-income countries, if these interventions are effective, and provide insights for implementers, policymakers, and researchers to amplify SV programming.

The review gathered and synthesised information from 41 peer-reviewed articles (published in PubMed and Web of Science between 2015 – 2023) that quantitatively measured the effectiveness of interventions to prevent or respond to SV from all 15 South-to-South Learning Network (SSLN) countries.

KEY FINDINGS

- ✓ SV prevention and response interventions occur at 3 levels:
 1. Primary prevention to prevent SV occurrence
 2. Secondary prevention to provide immediate response to SV survivors
 3. Tertiary prevention to provide long-term/ rehabilitation support to SV survivors
- ✓ Most studies to-date have evaluated primary prevention interventions

- ✓ Evaluated interventions show positive impact on SV outcomes

15 COUNTRIES OF FOCUS

FINDINGS

SV prevention and response interventions occur at 3 levels

Primary Prevention Interventions aim to prevent SV occurrence

Examples of primary prevention interventions include community sensitisation of SV, addressing gender equity and norms, etc.

Out of the 31 studies that focused on primary prevention, 84% showed an improvement in SV outcomes.

Secondary Prevention Interventions aim to respond immediately after SV has occurred

Examples of secondary prevention interventions include provision of medical services (PEP, STI treatment, emergency contraceptive provision), evaluation and treatment of injuries, referral to policy or social support, etc.

Out of the 6 studies that focused on secondary prevention, 100% showed an improvement in SV outcomes.

Tertiary Prevention Interventions focus on rehabilitation and long-term responses to SV

Examples of tertiary prevention programs include long-term psychosocial counselling, reintegration into family/ household, etc.

Out of the 8 studies that focused on tertiary prevention, 100% showed an improvement in SV outcomes.

INSIGHTS

APPLICABLE TO IMPLEMENTERS

DO	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> DO address entrenched gender norms by engaging community leaders DO enable sufficient number of exposures (10+) to the interventions over time when designing programmes DO include both the short-term and long-term response to SV in programmes DO build AGYW skills and self-efficacy through mentored safe space groups to prevent SV DO Integrate screening questions for SV into antenatal care and HIV service points to provide immediate care for SV DO provide psycho-social support through trauma-focused cognitive behavioural therapy or explore alternatives like art therapy to provide long-term support for victims of SV
DON'T	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> DON'T exclude parents and partners/ male peers in SV prevention/ response programming DON'T neglect training and support of community health workers who are often responsible for delivering SV programmes DON'T neglect to integrate opportunities to enhance HIV prevention in SV programming (e.g., offering PEP and PrEP) DON'T delay SV prevention programming with boys and girls; early adolescence is an opportune time to prevent SV DON'T neglect training for healthcare providers to screen for and provide supportive counselling for SV

APPLICABLE TO POLICYMAKERS

DO	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> DO dedicate funding and effort specifically for SV programming for AGYW DO ensure relevant evaluations in underrepresented regions like West Africa DO prioritise policies to support economic empowerment and access to education for AGYW
DON'T	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> DON'T overlook opportunities for integrating SV prevention within HIV platforms DON'T assume we know how to create supportive, respectful, and accessible police and judicial systems; evidence is needed

APPLICABLE TO RESEARCHERS

DO	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> DO recognise that there is a large evidence base for primary prevention strategies for SV DO expand the geography of where SV programs are tested (most of the evidence is from only a handful of countries in sub-Saharan Africa) DO de-link measures of violence so SV can be specifically tracked DO ensure that analyses segment results by age group, specifically for AGYW DO generate evidence for SV prevention interventions among marginalised populations (e.g., people with disabilities, sexual and gender minorities)
DON'T	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> DON'T ignore the need for testing secondary and tertiary prevention/ response approaches among AGYW

CONCLUSION

There is existing evidence on successful interventions to prevent and respond to SV among AGYW.

Following the Do's and Don'ts above should help strengthen SV interventions and enhance HIV outcomes. Coordinated action by implementers, policymakers, and researchers is needed to maximise current and future investments in SV programming and evidence generation.

SCAN HERE to find out more about SV among AGYW

PEP- Post-exposure Prophylaxis
PrEP- Pre-exposure prophylaxis
STI- Sexually Transmitted Infections

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